

Tactical Ballistic Missiles

Trajectory State & Error Covariance Propagation

by

Gary L. Sitzman and Gregory H. Drescher

Naval Surface Warfare Center, Dahlgren Division (NSWCDD)

Abstract

This paper addresses tracking Tactical Ballistic Missiles (TBMs) from space and ships. Modeling errors in the tracking system produce an uncertainty covariance matrix. Determining the critical error sources and identifying the needed elements of the covariance matrix is one analysis objective.

Given the shooter ship has received the TBM's state via a cue link, then a trajectory propagation model is needed to predict impact parameters and uncertainty error ellipses. Determining trajectory fidelity and quantifying the resulting errors is the second object of this paper.

I. Introduction

Tactical Ballistic Missiles are fast becoming a threat to world peace. To counter this threat requires the development of a new concept. One that combines the traditional players of target identification, communications, fire control, and the anti-ballistic missile. In this type of engagement, the total process is played on a compressed time line. Not minutes, but seconds and milli-seconds are the difference between success and failure.

This study will address only a small part of the total problem of Tactical Ballistic Missile Defense. Tracking accuracy, communication of accuracy data, and propagation of state and accuracy information will be discussed. TBMs with ranges between 200 and 3000 kilometers are the threat of concern.

II. Tracking Tactical Ballistic Missiles

Satellite Tracking

Tracking from space with satellites can certainly be effective in identifying missiles in-flight. Infrared sensors will detect missile plume. Continuous tracking is not necessary, but it is critical to track at a high rate during burnout. The largest error arises from the acceleration undetected between last track and burnout.

Tracking from satellites in space is depicted in figure 1, where passive infrared sensors are employed. The uncertainty in target state is illustrated by error ellipses about the estimated mean state value. Target estimated state and uncertainty will be sent to communication links for reception by Anti-Tactical Ballistic Missile platforms.

Figure 1. Tactical Ballistic Missile Defense (TBMD)

A family of TBMs were used in this study. Acceleration profiles for each TBM were integrated from launch to burnout. Burnout conditions were then propagated to impact under sample gravity fields. A family of launch points, flyout azimuths, and satellite measurement parameters depicted in figures 2 and 3 were used with each missile to determine the missile-tracker geometry effects.

Satellite Measurement Sigma - σ_m of Satellite measurement System (1000, 2000, and 5000 feet)
Launch Point - Grid (Latitude 0,30,60 Longitude 0,30,60)
Flyout Azimuth - 0, 45, and 90 degrees from north
Update spacing - Last update time x seconds before burnout.
Number of covariance elements to be transmitted at time of last update. (Full 6X6, 6, and 3)

Figure 2. Tactical Ballistic Missile Trajectory Parameters

Figure 3. Tracking & Estimating State Covariances of TBM's

Modeling the uncertainty in target TBM state was done by a simple Kalman filter with no process noise (figures 4-5). Error equations in method 1 assume no correlation between acceleration components and treat each component of acceleration as an independent error source. Method 2 assumes correlation is known between acceleration components and considers acceleration magnitude as an independent error source. Other error sources include initial state uncertainty, unknown acceleration between last track and burnout plus tracker measurement error.

State error equations: $\Delta \dot{\mathbf{R}} = \Delta \mathbf{V}$ $\Delta \dot{\mathbf{V}} = \mathbf{J} \cdot \Delta \mathbf{R} + \mathbf{f}(\bar{\mathbf{a}})$

<p>Method 1:</p> $\mathbf{f}(\bar{\mathbf{a}}) = \begin{pmatrix} SF_x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & SF_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & SF_z \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a_x \\ a_y \\ a_z \end{pmatrix}$ <p>** 3 Scale factors (x, y, and z) are evaluated as independent error sources</p> <p>State Covariance:</p> $\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_R^2 & \sigma_R \sigma_V & \sigma_R \sigma_{SF} \\ \sigma_V \sigma_R & \sigma_V^2 & \sigma_V \sigma_{SF} \\ \sigma_{SF} \sigma_R & \sigma_{SF} \sigma_V & \sigma_{SF}^2 \end{pmatrix}_{9 \times 9}$	<p>Method 2:</p> $\mathbf{f}(\bar{\mathbf{a}}) = (SF) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a_x \\ a_y \\ a_z \end{pmatrix}$ <p>** Only 1 scale factor used as an error source (acceleration magnitude)</p> <p>State Covariance:</p> $\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_R^2 & \sigma_R \sigma_V & \sigma_R \sigma_{SF} \\ \sigma_V \sigma_R & \sigma_V^2 & \sigma_V \sigma_{SF} \\ \sigma_{SF} \sigma_R & \sigma_{SF} \sigma_V & \sigma_{SF}^2 \end{pmatrix}_{7 \times 7}$
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Figure 4. Error Modeling for TBM State Estimation

Kalman Gain Matrix:

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{\Theta}^T (\mathbf{\Theta}\mathbf{C}^T + \mathbf{R})^{-1}$$

Covariance Update:

$$\mathbf{C}_{(+)} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{W}\mathbf{\Theta}) \mathbf{C}_{(-)}$$

Covariance Transition:

$$\mathbf{C}_{(t1)} = \mathbf{\Phi}_{(t0 \Rightarrow t1)} \mathbf{C}_{(t0)} \mathbf{\Phi}_{(t0 \Rightarrow t1)}^T$$

Figure 5. Standard Kalman Filtering Approach with no process noise

The infrared tracking measurement was simulated as the target's position error perpendicular to the tracker's line of sight to the target (figure 6).

Figure 6. Satellite Sensor Model

Results from space infrared tracking are shown in figures 7-10. Method 1, uncorrelated acceleration components, results in a mostly spherical error ellipse with component size proportional to acceleration magnitude. Method 2, known correlation with unknown magnitude, results in error ellipses elongated along the acceleration vector. Propagating only the variances from burnout to reentry results in small variations from propagation of the complete covariance. Conclusions are summarized in figure 11.

Figure 7. Position uncertainty at reentry for method 1 modeling.

Figure 8. Position Ellipses at Reentry, TBM-2 in X-Z Plane, Update interval 10 seconds, 2 satellites on X and Y axes, 13 Simultaneous Fixes, Burn out at 138.5 seconds

Figure 9. Position Ellipses at Reentry, TBM-2 in X-Z Plane, Update interval 10 seconds, 2 satellites on X and Y axes, 13 Simultaneous Fixes, Satellite estimated burn out at 135.0 seconds

Figure 10. Position Ellipses at Reentry, TBM-1 in X-Z Plane, Update interval 10 seconds, 2 satellites on X and Y axes, 8 Simultaneous Fixes, Burn out at 85 seconds

- Satellites should transmit Time, \bar{R} , \bar{V} , and 3 covariance parameters
 - Method 1: 3 σ 's in Polar Geocentric frame
 - Method 2: 3 σ 's in \bar{V}_{bo} , cross-track, in-track frame
- Burnout time uncertainty (Its effect on velocity sigmas) tends to dominate the other error sources
- No need to transmit position sigmas for satellite covariance

Figure 11. Conclusions for Space based infrared tracking

Ship Tracking

Radar tracking of TBMs during launch and reentry is also plausible. The primary advantage being their ability to track during and after burnout. Actually, enough data to estimate the targets state vector can be obtained during a brief tracking period after burnout. The disadvantages of these active trackers are their power requirement and limited range to the target.

Tracking from surface ships is depicted in figure 12, where active radar sensors are employed. Hand-off from launch point tracking to ship tracking in the impact area is represented. The radar tracking measurement was simulated as the complete position error.

Figure 12. Ship Radar Tracking and Covariance Hand-Off Study

Only method 2 was used in ships tracking. Radar parameters are shown in figure 13.

Figure 13. Ship Tracking Radar Parameters

Radar tracking from ships shows significantly different results from satellite tracking (figure 14).

Figure 14. Radar error ellipse (shown at reentry)

III. Communication of Tracking Data

Communication of state vectors and covariance data from sensors to communication links to launch platforms is the conduit through which defense against Tactical Ballistic Missiles is achieved. The data has a very brief half life of value and the conduit has a thruput limit. Hence we are faced with the question of how can the input be reduced without destroying the output. Obviously, the state vector (time, position, velocity) is the most important. If the target is maneuvering, then frequent updates are required. If the target is in free-fall, few updates to the track are needed.

Uncertainty in estimated position and velocity of the TBM is represented by the covariance matrix. The variances and correlation coefficients define the shape and orientation of the error ellipse. Correlation coefficients are zero when the error ellipse is symmetric about the coordinate frame it is written in. If the shape is skewed, then the variances and orientation data are needed to define the ellipse. Ultimate use of the covariance is to construct a radar search pattern (figures 15-16). Using a search pattern that covers the ellipse (size, shape, and orientation) will conserve valuable radar resources by limiting the search to only the most probable areas of the sky.

A sensitivity study was performed to determine the elements of the target state covariance matrix that need to be transmitted to the shooter. Propagation of the covariance from burnout to radar acquisition near reentry is accomplished via a transition matrix (figure 15).

Figure 15. Ship use of Satellite Transmitted Data

“truth” trajectory model. In the study each parameter was tested independently while holding all other settings at their nominal value. The nominal trajectory was run to a stopping altitude of 10 km and this nominal intercept time was used to stop the perturbed trajectories creating a three dimensional position error.

Figure 17. TBM Trajectory Trade-off Study

Figure 16. Radar search pattern

Figure 18. TBM (TBM-1 and TBM-2) Trajectories

IV. Trajectory State Propagation

The acquisition radar will receive target data via a communication link. The data will represent target state estimates and state uncertainty at burnout or time of last track. The ship will propagate these data to a point where it can begin to acquire the target (figure 17). The trajectory model used to propagate the state should be of a fidelity consistent with the uncertainty in the initial state.

A sensitivity study was performed for short and long range trajectories (figure 18) to determine model complexity needed. A truth trajectory model was defined to include the highest order gravity field, a fourth order integration routine, standard atmosphere, and truth aero data. Bulleted items in figure 19 make up the nominal

<u>Gravity Fields</u>	<u>Reentry Atmospheres</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WGS-84 Tesseral 9X9 field WGS-84 Oblate Inverse Square Flat Earth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standard Exponential
<u>Integration Schemes</u>	<u>Drag Models</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4th order Runge-Kutta 2nd order Runge-Kutta Trapezoidal Kepler (inverse square closed form) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ballistic coefficient (sensitivity) Functional offset
* Indicates truth model setting	

Figure 19. Trajectory Trade-Off Parameters

Errors resulting in reducing the complexity of this modeling were computed and are depicted in figures 20-21. In the two figures the height of each bar represents the RSS position error over all test cases. The width of each bar, excluding the ballistic coefficient sensitivities, represents the increase in computation speed over the nominal. The area of each bar then can be used to gauge each model's performance. The ballistic coefficient bars show the RSS position error incurred by errors in the ballistic coefficient of 10, 20, 30, and 40 percent. The width of the ballistic coefficient bars are not shown to scale because they do not represent a reduction in model complexity and therefore do not increase computation speed. The nominal bar is shown as a baseline.

Conclusions of the study are shown in figure 22.

Figure 20. Trajectory Model Performance TBM-1

Figure 21. Trajectory Model Performance TBM-2

- Oblate gravity field
- Standard Atmosphere
- Fourth order Runge-Kutta with variable integration step size
 - Large Δt in vacuum
 - Smaller Δt through re-entry

Figure 22. Suggested State Propagation Model

V. Conclusions

Space/ship tracking of TBMs is practical and efficient. Cueing data consists of target state and a "subset" of the covariance matrix. Covariance data is ultimately needed to generate a search pattern for the shooter radar, and as a result can be considerably reduced in size with little or no effect on system performance. Trajectory fidelity for propagation of the target state vector will be selected based on availability of computer resources and initial state vector fidelity.

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